

Stimulating physical activity in hard-to-reach physically disabled people; systematic development of a community-based intervention

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Abstract PURPOSE: Physically disabled people participate less in physical activity (PA) than healthy people. Most existing PA interventions are rehabilitation- or school based, limiting their reach. The current study aims to develop a community-based intervention for stimulating PA in hard-to-reach physically disabled people. METHODS: Intervention Mapping (6 steps) was used for systematically developing a PA intervention. Health related quality of life (HRQoL) of physically disabled people was measured using the RAND-36. Requirements on an intervention were investigated using qualitative research among experts and physically disabled people. RESULTS: HRQoL was poorer in physically disabled people compared to healthy people (step 1). Since experts expressed no need for a new intervention, the existing intervention "Activity coach" (Dutch: Beweegcoach) was adapted to the requirements of experts and the target population. Within the adapted intervention, "Activity coach+", participants will be reached by a network of intermediate organizations. Participants will have a physical assessment by physiotherapists, and will be individually guided to organized or non-organized activities by an activity coach. Participants will monitor and set goals for daily PA using an activity tracker. Participants will be coached one year (step 4). Activity coaches were trained and network meetings were organized to support adoption and implementation (step 5). Activity coach+ is implemented in community March 2017, and will be evaluated using a mixed-method design. PA will be objectively monitored, and health effects will be evaluated using questionnaires and physical assessments after 0, 2, 4, 6 and 12 months. Experiences with the intervention will be determined using qualitative research (step 6). CONCLUSION: Activity Coach+ included a community-based intervention for stimulating both organized and non-organized PA in hard-to-reach physically disabled people, and is currently under evaluation.

Keywords Intervention Mapping, physical activity, disability, health promotion

Introduction

As in healthy people, physical activity (PA) participation benefits health and functioning in physically disabled people. Despite the health benefits, physically disabled people participate less

in PA compared with healthy people. Scientific interest for PA in physically disabled people is currently shifting from describing barriers and facilitators towards designing interventions to stimulate PA participation in physically disabled people.

Most existing PA interventions for physically disabled people approach their target populations via intermediate organizations, what limits their reach (von Heijden, van den Dool et al. 2013). The current study aims to describe the systematic intervention development, and design for the implementation and evaluation of a community-based PA-stimulating intervention in hard-to-reach physically disabled adults.

Methods

The stepwise methodology of Intervention Mapping (IM) was applied for the systematic intervention development, and the design of the implementation and evaluation plan (Bartholomew, Parcel et al. 2011).

Results

IM step 1: Needs assessment

PA participation of physically disabled people was lower compared with healthy people. In former rehabilitation patients, the amount of PA was positively related to all domains of HRQoL (RAND-36), except for mental health.

IM step 2: Performance objectives and change objectives

The main outcome of the intervention is increased PA participation. Resulting from qualitative research amongst professionals and the target population, PA participation can be subdivided into the following performance objectives: increasing participation in organized PA, non-organized PA and activities of daily living (ADL). These performance objectives are influenced by several determinants (eg. knowledge). Change objectives were formulated by crossing performance objectives and determinants. One of the change objectives is that participants know possible organized activities to participate in.

IM step 3: Theory-based intervention methods and practical applications

For all change objectives, theory-based methods were selected from behavioral science models. Based on qualitative research amongst professionals and the target population these theory-based methods were translated into the following six different practical applications: role-models, information by health professionals, pre-intervention capacity assessment, overviews presenting possible facilities for becoming physically active, activity monitoring, and a buddy system.

IM step 4: Intervention program

The existing PA-stimulating intervention 'Activity Coach' included several of the methods and practical applications described in step 3. Based on the demands of professionals and the target population, 'Activity Coach' was further developed into 'Activity Coach+' (figure 1).

Potential participants of Activity Coach+ will be recruited by a network of intermediate organizations (eg. home care, welfare, general practitioners) and local media. Participants will have a physiotherapeutic intake, including history taking and physical assessment. Participants will be individually coached by the activity coach during one year. Organized PA will be stimulated

by overviews of possible activities, non-organized PA will be stimulated by connecting buddies, and PA during ADL will be stimulated by goal setting using a Fitbit Zip activity tracker (figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the adapted intervention 'Activity Coach+'.

IM step 5: Adoption, implementation and sustainability

All intermediate organizations will be invited for an introduction meeting, and will receive news messages. Guidelines for the execution of the intervention are provided to the activity coaches, and attractive flyers will be distributed among participants.

IM step 6: Evaluation plan

Activity Coach+ will be pilot tested in three municipalities in the Northern Netherlands. The implementation process will be evaluated using qualitative research among professionals and participants. The effectiveness will be evaluated using a 1-year prospective cohort study, with measurements at baseline, 2, 4, 6 and 12 months evaluating PA behavior, bio psychosocial health and functioning.

Conclusion and discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study describing the systematic development of a community-based intervention to stimulate PA in hard-to-reach physically disabled people. The implementation process and effectiveness of Activity Coach+ will be evaluated in future research.

References

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